

WP5 - Getting actors to act: dissemination, exploitation and communication

Plan to Boost Digital Tools for Agroforestry

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Contents

1.	Context	3
2.	Introduction	3
3.	Baseline for uptake: maturity and readiness of DigitAF Tools	3
4.	Uptake roadmap	5
4.1.	Policy actors	5
4.2.	Practitioners - Integration into advisory services and farm-level decision support	7
4.3.	Value chain - Market development and voluntary certification pathways	8
5.	Networking and community building strategy	11
5.1.	Developer and technical community engagement	12
5.2.	Community stewards and institutional anchoring	12
5.3.	Cross-Project collaboration and knowledge exchange	12

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WP5 - Getting actors to act: dissemination, exploitation and communication

5.4.	Practitioner and advisory network activation	13
6.	Good Practices for FAIR-Aligned Digital Development	14
6.1.	Technical Framework for High-Quality Monitoring and Verification (MRV)	14
6.2.	Enhancing Interoperability with Administrative Datasets (LPIS)	15
6.3.	Strategies for Long-term Tool Reusability and Open Evolution	15
7.	Communication and capacity building actions	15
7.1.	Policy and knowledge outputs	15
7.2.	Training and engagement activities	17
7.3.	Digital dissemination tools	18
8.	Monitoring, risks and timeline	19
8.1.	Monitoring framework and key performance indicators	19
8.2.	Key risks affecting long-term sustainability	21
8.3.	Mitigation strategies and resilience design	22
8.4.	Outlook and post-project evolution	22
9.	Conclusions	23
10.	Acknowledgements	23

WP5 - Getting actors to act: dissemination, exploitation and communication

1. Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three actors' groups that are target by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This report is relevant for the communication about the project and dissemination to all three stakeholders' groups. It presents the DigitAF roadmap for long-term uptake, dissemination, and sustainability of agroforestry digital tools and datasets beyond the project lifetime (2026). It outlines how tools, data infrastructures, and community networks developed within DigitAF will be maintained, reused, and further evolved within an open, FAIR-aligned digital ecosystem. The document also describes strategies for policy engagement, practitioner adoption, and value-chain integration, alongside governance, monitoring, and risk mitigation mechanisms to ensure continuity and impact.

2. Introduction

The DigitAF project (2022–2026) develops and connects digital tools, datasets, and decision-support systems to accelerate the adoption of agroforestry across Europe. This deliverable defines the roadmap for ensuring that these outputs remain usable, visible, and actively maintained beyond the end of the project, transitioning from a time-bound research initiative into a distributed, community-driven digital ecosystem.

The strategy is aligned with broader EU objectives on climate neutrality, sustainable land use, and data-driven policy development under the Green Deal. It focuses on ensuring that agroforestry knowledge becomes operational through interoperable tools, persistent data infrastructures, and open dissemination channels that support policy actors, practitioners, and value-chain stakeholders.

3. Baseline for uptake: maturity and readiness of DigitAF Tools

3.1. Overview of the Digital Ecosystem

The baseline consists of a centralized Agroforestry Tools, Data and Projects Catalogue. Currently, the project has identified and catalogued (Fig 1):

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- 56 specialized digital tools.
- 46 key datasets relevant agroforestry.
- 81 agroforestry-related projects.

Figure 1. The Agroforestry Tools, Data, and Projects catalogues provide a consolidated access point to the DigitAF digital ecosystem, currently hosting 56 tools, 46 datasets, and 81 projects. These resources include a growing number of recent additions over the last three months, reflecting ongoing community engagement and continuous expansion of the knowledge base.

3.2. Tool Maturity and Readiness Framework (FAIRness Score)

DigitAF does not just list tools; it evaluates their readiness for uptake using a customized FAIRness Scoring methodology. This baseline assessment measures maturity across four dimensions:

- Findability (F): Presence of unique identifiers (DOIs) and full documentation.
- Accessibility (A): Ease of access (e.g., direct download vs. registration), language availability, and training materials.
- Interoperability (I): Use of standard file formats (CSV, JSON) and APIs to allow different tools to "talk" to each other.
- Reusability (R): Clear usage licenses (e.g., GPL, MIT) and well-described development processes.

3.3. Current Readiness of Core DigitAF Tools

The baseline for specific tools that have been "FAIRified" and improved includes:

- Hi-sAFe: Transitioning from a researcher-focused model towards a more openly accessible and documented version, with improved microclimate and CO₂ response formalisms.
- Agrofores TreeAdvice: A unified interface has been built to consolidate multiple independent tree selection tools (DENTRO, DECIDUOUS, SCSM, Shade TreeAdvice, Goöko HeckenManager, JBOJP, a Czech database, a Finnish database, a swiss database, a UK database) into a single entry point.
- LPIS Sustainability Compass: A prototype tool using existing Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) data to help farmers benchmark their sustainability against regional averages.
- Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator: A Beta-version tool developed from 62 European case studies to estimate biodiversity changes based on farm design.

- CARAT: Enhanced through integration of the LPIS API, enabling the use of harmonised parcel boundaries and administrative data within the tool, while supporting its migration from R to Python.
- Open Farm Carbon Tracker (OFCT): Developed as an open-source web application for farm-level carbon accounting, with integration of the LPIS API to enable direct use of harmonised parcel boundaries and improve spatial consistency across assessments.

3.4. Maturity Bottlenecks Identified in Living Labs

Surveys across six Living Labs provide the baseline for user-readiness:

- Low Awareness: Many practitioners are unaware of existing tools (e.g., 74% of respondents were unaware of AF design tools) (Tranchina et al 2024)
- Usability Needs: Stakeholders demand mobile-friendly tools that work offline and offer intuitive graphical interfaces.
- Data Gaps: A significant hurdle is the lack of long-term, site-specific data to validate predictive models, which currently impacts user trust.
- Data Accessibility: Stakeholders highlighted the need for direct, automated access to datasets. While Copernicus data can be accessed through APIs, limited automation options for some JRC datasets create barriers to tool integration and operational use.

4. Uptake roadmap

4.1. Policy actors - agroforestry regulations, at regional, national and European levels

The long-term strategy for policy uptake centres on the "LPIS Sustainability Compass" and the "LPIS Aggregator" as primary vehicles for advocacy.

- *Promoting data openness and improved land-use reporting:* the LPIS Integrator (LPIS API) services leverage the availability of national LPIS datasets to provide evidence-based insights into agricultural land use. By enabling comparison between administrative parcel data and global land-use datasets, these tools highlight classification inconsistencies (e.g. agroforestry misidentified as forest) and support arguments for more accurate CAP reporting and recognition of agroforestry systems.

LPIS Integrator (LPIS API Access Tool)	https://lpis.regenfarmer.com/	
	Type	Spatial data integration
	Objective	Bridge administrative Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) data with agroforestry design tools by enabling direct access to official parcel boundaries and land-use metadata for spatial planning and analysis.
	Target	Researchers, GIS developers,

	users	Advisors
Current status	Operational web-based interface and API providing access to LPIS vector tile data from multiple European countries (including AT, BE, CZ, DK, FI, FR, DE, IE, NL, PT), alongside associated metadata such as crop references, land-use classifications, and administrative boundaries.	
Uptake mechanism	Enables seamless integration of official parcel geometries into agroforestry planning workflows. This supports precise farm-level design (e.g. tree row layout, buffer zones) while reducing entry barriers associated with manual digitisation and improving spatial accuracy in downstream analyses.	
Long-term sustainability	Serves as a foundational access layer for agroforestry digital tools by ensuring that spatial analyses are grounded in authoritative administrative datasets. Its API-based structure enables continued reuse and integration into external applications, supporting long-term interoperability across the digital agroforestry ecosystem and related agroforestry decision-support systems. https://github.com/regen-farmer/lpis-showcase	

- *Carbon Removal Certification*: The Open Farm Carbon Tracker acts as a technical baseline to lobby for the inclusion of complex agroforestry systems in the EU’s Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), providing the 90% accuracy benchmarks required by regulators.

Open Farm Carbon Tracker		https://openfarmcarbontracker.onrender.com/
		<p>Type</p> <p>Open-source decision-support tool</p> <p>Objective</p> <p>Estimate farm-level carbon balances for agroforestry systems</p> <p>Target users</p> <p>Farmers, advisors, certification actors</p>
Current status	Publicly available web application and GitHub repository	
Uptake mechanism	Supports voluntary carbon markets and CRCF-aligned assessments	
Long-term sustainability	Maintained through EURAF GitHub ecosystem under open-source licensing - https://github.com/euraf/OpenFarmCarbonTracker	

4.2. Practitioners - Integration into advisory services and farm-level decision support

This pathway focuses on embedding DigitAF tools into practical workflows to assist farmers and advisors in evaluating management options.

- *Benchmarking and Design*: Tools like the LPIS Sustainability Compass allow farmers to visualize their parcels alongside Copernicus Earth observation data to identify "tree-desert" areas. This

facilitates ex-ante evaluations of adopting new practices like riparian buffers or silvoarable strips.

LPIS Sustainability Compass (LPIS-SC)		https://mvagroecology.github.io/lucim/lpis-sustainability-compass	
	Type	Web-based GIS decision-support tool / indicator-based assessment system	
	Objective	Provide farm-level sustainability insights by aggregating LPIS-based spatial data and generating indicators to support agroforestry-related planning and policy-relevant decision-making	
	Target users	Farmers, advisors, policymakers, land-use planners, researchers	
Current status	Operational prototype available online with public web interface and open-source code repository. The tool is currently being tested and iteratively improved based on feedback from Living Labs and stakeholder engagement		
Uptake mechanism	Enables translation of LPIS spatial datasets into actionable sustainability indicators, supporting farm-level decision-making, advisory services, and policy-relevant assessments for agroforestry adoption		
Long-term sustainability	The tool follows an open-development approach, with its code publicly available and open to contributions. Long-term maintenance is expected to be ensured through transfer to community governance within the broader agroforestry stakeholder network		

- **Economic Reality Checks:** Integration into advisory services involves using models like Farm-SAFE, INTACT and AgroForstRechner to move beyond simple gross margins toward long-term Annuity and Net Present Value (NPV) assessments. This helps advisors counter the "long time to revenue" barrier that currently discourages adoption.

Economic Decision-Support Tools		Farm-SAFE https://dspace.lib.cranfield.ac.uk/handle/1826/22350 INTACT https://www.agroforestryvlaanderen.be/en/agroforestry-planner-2 AgroForstRechner https://agroforst-info.de/agroforstrechner/	
	Type	Economic tools / decision-support models	
	Objective	Support economic evaluation of agroforestry systems beyond short-term gross margins, focusing on long-term profitability and investment appraisal	
	Target users	Farmers, advisors, policymakers, researchers, financial stakeholders	

Current status	Set of operational and prototype tools available within the DigitAF ecosystem, supporting economic assessment of agroforestry adoption scenarios
Uptake mechanism	Enables evidence-based financial decision-making by supporting assessment of long-term economic performance, investment viability, and risk reduction in agroforestry transitions
Long-term sustainability	Designed for continued reuse and adaptation within open agroforestry knowledge networks, supporting integration into advisory services and future decision-support ecosystems

4.3. Value chain - Market development and voluntary certification pathways

This pathway focuses on supporting the development of agroforestry value chains through digital tools and data products that enable voluntary certification, sustainability claims, and improved market visibility.

- *Carbon and Biodiversity Crediting*: The Open Farm Carbon Tracker and Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator (BiodivAF) provide the quantitative "story" needed by value chain actors like wholesalers and retailers to justify price premiums. These tools enable stakeholders to trade sequestration and biodiversity benefits with verified, farm-level evidence.

BiodivAF Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator		https://biodivaf.shinyapps.io/BiodivAF/	
<p>Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator (beta) Select biodiversity metrics First select the agroforestry system type and the biodiversity indicators you wish to explore. Agroforestry System Type: Agroforestry Invertebrates: Abundance/Activity * <input type="checkbox"/> Aboveground Invertebrates: Abundance/Activity * <input type="checkbox"/> Pest species: Mean plot richness * <input type="checkbox"/> <small>* Models marked with an asterisk showed low predictive performance and should be interpreted with caution.</small></p>		Type	Web-based decision-support tool
		Objective	Assess potential biodiversity gains associated with agroforestry implementation using evidence derived from European case studies
		Target users	Farmers, advisors, researchers, certification actors, policymakers
Current status	Publicly accessible beta-version application developed from DigitAF biodiversity indicator methodologies (Vandendriessche et al. 2023) and based on data from 62 European case studies (Vandendriessche et al. 2025)		
Uptake mechanism	Supports biodiversity assessment, sustainability communication, and voluntary certification pathways by providing standardized estimates of biodiversity co-benefits linked to agroforestry practices		
Long-term sustainability	Hosted as an openly accessible web application, with underlying methodologies and datasets publicly available through the DigitAF		

	ecosystem; future open-source release of the full codebase is subject to ongoing scientific publication processes
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- *Branding and Actor Discovery*: The Agroforestry Map of Europe serves as the discovery layer for the value chain, geolocating not just farms but also nurseries, processors, and "Agroforestry Ambassadors". This reduces the "lack of marketing skills" barrier identified in Living Labs by connecting producers directly to retailers seeking sustainable sourcing.

Agroforestry Map of Europe		https://digitaf.eu/agroforestry-map/ https://euraf.net/agroforestry-map-of-europe/	
	Type	Interactive mapping and stakeholder discovery platform	
	Objective	Increase the visibility and connectivity of agroforestry actors, initiatives, and value-chain stakeholders across Europe	
	Target users	Farmers, advisors, researchers, policymakers, nurseries, processors, agroforestry organisations, consumers	
Current status	Publicly accessible multilingual platform co-developed within the DigitAF and REFOREST projects, integrated across multiple institutional websites and supported by a shared centralised database		
Uptake mechanism	Facilitates actor discovery, peer-to-peer networking, advisory support, and market development by enabling users to identify agroforestry stakeholders and initiatives at local, national, and European scales		
Long-term sustainability	Sustained through continued dissemination and collaborative use across the DigitAF and REFOREST projects, the EURAF network, and participating national agroforestry organisations, which contribute to ongoing visibility, data validation, and expansion of the platform		

Together, these components contribute to structuring agroforestry value chains by combining open analytical tools, evidence-based assessment frameworks, and actor mapping functionalities to support certification, branding, and market development pathways.

4.4. Research and innovation uptake

This section addresses the technical community and future developers to ensure the DigitAF legacy continues in the scientific domain.

- FAIRness as a Standard: All project tools are evaluated via an automated FAIRness Scoring methodology (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability). This score serves as a guide for future researchers to integrate DigitAF modules into new innovations.

FAIRness Scoring and Self-Assessment Framework		Tools FAIRness Self-Assessment https://euraf.github.io/AF_FAIRness/tools/fairness_self_assessment Datasets FAIRness Self-Assessment https://euraf.github.io/AF_FAIRness/data/fairness_self_assessment	
		Type	Digital evaluation and self-assessment framework
		Objective	Operationalise the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) through a structured scoring system that helps users and developers assess, compare, and improve the FAIRness of agroforestry digital tools and datasets.
		Target users	Tool developers, data providers, researchers, policymakers, advisors
Current status	A FAIRness scoring system (Tomás et al. 2024) is implemented within the DigitAF Agroforestry Tool and Data Catalogues, providing an automatically calculated and human-verified multi-dimensional assessment of digital resources. A complementary self-assessment tool enables developers and data providers to evaluate their own resources prior to submission, with real-time feedback on how individual responses affect overall FAIR scores.		
Uptake mechanism	Supports improved discovery, integration, and reuse of agroforestry digital resources by translating FAIR principles into practical questions and interpretable indicators. The system enables users to quickly identify strengths and weaknesses of tools and datasets, guiding improvements in documentation, accessibility, interoperability, and licensing, while also supporting better-informed selection and integration of resources (e.g. interoperability-focused users prioritising high I-scores).		
Long-term sustainability	Embedded as a continuous evaluation layer within the DigitAF digital ecosystem, the framework supports ongoing improvement of tool and data quality. By combining automated scoring with user-driven self-assessment, it fosters iterative enhancement of FAIRness across agroforestry digital resources and encourages sustained community engagement in improving openness and interoperability standards.		

- *Open Software Evolution*: Transitioning core researcher-only code (e.g., Hi-sAFe's Java code) to open GitHub repositories under GPL licenses removes the "co-authorship requirement" for usage, fostering independent scientific validation and extension by the global community, while fragmented tree selection tools (e.g. AgroforesTreeAdvice) are being harmonised to improve interoperability and reuse across advisory applications.

FAIR Transition of Software		Hi-SAFE https://github.com/hisafe AgroforesTreeAdvice https://github.com/euraf/agroforestreeteetadvice	
	Type	Digital tool transition and harmonisation	
	Objective	Improve the FAIRness of agroforestry digital tools: two complementary pathways: (i) transitioning core modelling tools towards open, transparent and citable research infrastructures, and (ii) harmonising fragmented decision-support tools into integrated, comparable advisory systems.	
	Target users	Tool developers, researchers	
Current status	<p><i>Model transition pathway:</i> core agroforestry simulation tools (e.g. Hi-sAFe) are being progressively made more accessible, documented, and citable through FAIR-aligned release practices and persistent identifiers.</p> <p><i>Tool harmonisation pathway:</i> tree selection and decision-support tools (e.g. AgroforesTreeAdvice (Gosme et al. 2025), integrating approaches from ten previously existing tools or databases) are being structurally aligned to reduce fragmentation and improve comparability.</p>		
Uptake mechanism	Enhances usability and adoption by (i) increasing transparency, accessibility, and citability of complex models, and (ii) enabling consistent data structures and harmonised decision criteria across previously fragmented tree selection tools, improving advisory coherence and user understanding.		
Long-term sustainability	Strengthens the agroforestry digital ecosystem by supporting long-term reusability of core models through FAIR-aligned publication practices, and by enabling convergence of dispersed decision-support tools into interoperable, comparable frameworks that reduce duplication and improve advisory consistency.		

5. Networking and community building strategy

The strategy centers on transitioning the project's digital assets from a closed research environment to a permanent, community-driven ecosystem hosted by the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF).

5.1. Developer and technical community engagement

Establishment of an open agroforestry developer community anchored in the European Agroforestry Federation ecosystem, enabling collaborative development, peer review, and reuse of DigitAF tools.

This includes:

- shared code practices and lightweight contribution guidelines: transitioning to GitHub enables peer review, version control, and lightweight contribution guidelines (e.g., using PyGitHub for automated validation).
- visibility and recognition for contributors (e.g. featured tools, contributor profiles): the Agroforestry Tools, Data and Projects Catalogue provides visibility through “featured tools” and a “latest contributors” section, enhancing recognition of developers beyond the project lifetime, incentivising continued maintenance of existing tools and encouraging ongoing contributions of new resources.

5.2. Community stewards and institutional anchoring

Long-term continuity is supported through a distributed stewardship model involving key institutional actors. The European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF), together with national agroforestry organisations and project partners, acts as a coordinating and facilitating network rather than a centralised owner of digital assets.

These organisations support:

- continuity of community engagement
- alignment between research, practice, and policy needs
- validation and contextualisation of digital resources
- dissemination and uptake across national and regional contexts

This distributed model ensures that responsibility for ecosystem continuity is shared across institutions and user communities.

5.3. Cross-Project collaboration and knowledge exchange

DigitAF actively promotes interoperability and coordination with related European research and innovation initiatives, including ongoing agroforestry-related projects such as REFOREST.

Collaboration focuses on:

- avoid duplication of digital tools: the Agroforestry Map of Europe was co-developed (with REFOREST) to provide a single entry point for stakeholders, preventing the "scattered information" problem identified by users.
- promote interoperability and shared standards
- co-develop new functionalities where synergies exist

This ensures that DigitAF outputs contribute to a broader, connected European agroforestry digital ecosystem rather than isolated project-specific solutions.

5.4. Practitioner and advisory network activation

Engagement with end-users is ensured through structured collaboration with practitioner networks, advisory services, and national agroforestry organisations. These actors function as intermediaries between digital tools and real-world application contexts.

Key mechanisms include:

- integration with national agroforestry associations: national agroforestry organizations act as validation channels for geolocated data on the European Agroforestry map, ensuring the tool remains relevant at the local scale.
- creation of feedback loops between end-users and developers: stakeholder surveys in the 6 Living Labs have identified critical usability needs, such as offline functionality and mobile-optimized interfaces, which directly inform the next iteration of tool development. After initial presentation of tools in Living Labs, stakeholders chose the tools they wanted to test (Table 1). Then the selected tools were tested by end-users, who provided feedback to tool developers.

Table 1: List of digital tools tested in the six DigitAF Living Labs

	CZ	FIN	Living Lab		NL	IT
			UK	GER		
Species selection						
AgroforesTreeAdvice	1	1			1	
Agromix App						1
Agroforestry system design and decision support						
Agroforestry Planner (BETULA)					1	
"Entscheidungshilfe" Decision-Helper				1		
RegenWorks	1	1			1	1
FarmTree Tool	1				1	1
GoOko-Heckenmanager				1		
Carbon						
Cool Farm Tool	1	1				1
CARAT	1	1		1		
Open Farm Carbon Tracker		1	1			
CarboCatch	1	1			1	
AgreCalc			1			
Farm Carbon Calculator			1			
Farm Carbon Toolkit		1				
Economic						
INTACT	1				1	1
farmSAFE	1		1			1
AgroForstRechner				1		
Rekenmodel Agroforestry					1	
FarmTree tool					1	
Social / Community						
Agroforestry Map of Europe		1		1		1
Qanda/AI4A tool		1				
Performance/Growth						
Woodland Code Dataset		1				
Yield-SAFE	1		1		1	
YieldSAFE with RothC			1		1	1
Biodiversity, water, soil health						
Farmland biodiversity credit point system						
Cool Farm Tool (Biodiversity)	1	1				
UKCEH Soil Health Tool		1				1

This ensures that DigitAF outputs remain relevant, usable, and aligned with practical decision-making needs across diverse agroforestry contexts.

6. Good Practices for FAIR-Aligned Digital Development

6.1. Technical Framework for High-Quality Monitoring and Verification (MRV)

To meet the rigorous requirements of the EU's Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), digital tools must achieve high accuracy and transparency.

- **Model Accuracy:** Tools should aim for a 90% accuracy benchmark by integrating harmonized field protocols—such as standardized soil sampling for bulk density and SOC—to provide "ground truth" for model validation.
- **Handling Complexity:** Avoid generic IPCC Tier 1 values; instead, develop models capable of simulating the "infinite combinations" of tree-crop species and spatial patterns characteristic of agroforestry.
- **Transparency:** Clearly document all biophysical models and simplifying assumptions within the tool's metadata to ensure user trust and scientific validity.

6.2. Enhancing Interoperability with Administrative Datasets (LPIS)

A core "good practice" is the seamless integration of existing European administrative data into new digital workflows.

- **Automating Data Inputs:** Use API-based structures, like the LPIS Integrator, to allow tools to automatically pull official parcel boundaries and land-use metadata. This reduces the entry barrier for farmers by eliminating manual digitization.
- **Spatially Explicit Insights:** Combine LPIS data with Copernicus Earth observation data to help users identify "tree-deserts" and benchmark their sustainability against local regional reference conditions.
- **Standardized Schemas:** Adopt consistent data structures and crop reference codes across tools to ensure that spatial analyses remain grounded in authoritative administrative datasets.

6.3. Strategies for Long-term Tool Reusability and Open Evolution

To prevent technical obsolescence, the development process must prioritize open-source code, permissive licenses and community maintenance.

- **Open Licensing:** Core software code (e.g., different models and tools) should be released under permissive licenses like MIT or Apache to allow for independent scientific validation and adaptation by third parties.
- **Modular Architecture:** Design tools as decentralized, serverless applications, such as the DigitAF Agroforestry Gallery, that query open APIs (like Zenodo) rather than relying on private, high-maintenance backends.

- Contributor Recognition: Use platforms like GitHub to establish "contributor profiles" and lightweight guidelines, incentivizing developers to maintain tools beyond the project's formal end date.

7. Communication and capacity building actions

This section describes the communication, training, and dissemination mechanisms that ensure DigitAF outputs are effectively transferred into practice. It focuses on knowledge packaging, capacity building, and digital dissemination infrastructures that support uptake across policy, research, and practitioner communities.

7.1. Policy and knowledge outputs

- *Persistent Scientific Legacy*: All policy briefings (WP1) and public deliverables are assigned Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and archived in the Zenodo EURAF Community. This ensures that technical outputs remain accessible after the project concludes in June 2026.

Policy Briefings and Reports on Deliverables		https://digitaf.eu/policy-briefings/ https://digitaf.eu/reports-on-deliverables/	
	Type	Integrated knowledge dissemination	
	Objective	Provide transparent, structured, and policy-relevant access to DigitAF knowledge outputs by combining concise policy briefings and full project deliverables into a unified dissemination framework.	
	Target users	Policymakers, researchers, practitioners, advisory services, EU institutions, and agroforestry stakeholders	
Current status	Policy briefings (WP1) and all public project deliverables are archived in the Zenodo EURAF Community ¹ , where they are assigned persistent identifiers (DOIs) ensuring citability, version control, and long-term open access. Both output types are also dynamically displayed on the DigitAF website through an automated integration system.		
Uptake mechanism	Supports uptake by offering a dual-layer knowledge system: concise policy briefings for rapid decision-making and full deliverables for technical depth and reproducibility. This structure improves accessibility of evidence generated by DigitAF tools and supports policy development, research reuse, and practical implementation.		
Long-term sustainability	Ensures long-term availability and reuse through DOI-based archival in Zenodo and continuous web integration, maintaining accessibility, traceability, and visibility of both policy-oriented and technical outputs beyond the project lifetime.		

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/euraf>

- *Practice Abstracts*: DigitAF produced a series of practice abstracts in the EIP-AGRI format, covering financial and marketing aspects, technical innovations, machinery, and environmental impacts of agroforestry. These are compiled in Deliverables D5.8 (Bernascone et al. 2023) and D5.9 (Gosme et al. 2026). Although they were prepared for wider dissemination through the EIP-AGRI network, they are currently available mainly as project deliverables. They remain a useful resource for future dissemination through advisory services, practitioner networks, and other knowledge-sharing activities.
- *Persistent publication of research datasets*: DigitAF also ensures long-term accessibility of key research datasets through deposition in Zenodo. Examples include agrobiodiversity occurrence data from tree-row bordered cereal fields in Flanders (Vandendriessche et al. 2026) and human-verified bat acoustic recordings (Vandendriessche & Vandendriessche 2026), both published as open datasets with DOIs, supporting reuse, transparency, and reproducibility of project results.

7.2. Training and engagement activities

The image shows a YouTube interface with a search bar and navigation icons. Below the search bar is a video player showing a thumbnail for 'DigitAF webinars available in replay on DigitAF website'. Below the player is a grid of four webinar thumbnails with titles: 'Tools on Carbon Farming (REPLAY)', 'Financial Tools for Agroforestry (REPLAY)', 'Biodiversity and Soil Health (REPLAY)', and 'Trees and Management (REPLAY)'. To the right is a playlist titled '#DIGITAFTOOLS' with four items: '#DIGITAFTOOLS - Deciduous', '#DIGITAFTOOLS - AgroforestAR Indoor', '#DIGITAFTOOLS - Shade Tree Advice', and '#DIGITAFTOOLS - CARAT'. Each item has a video thumbnail and a duration.

Capacity-building activities focus on the technical transfer of project results to end-users and stakeholders. **A central component of this framework is the #DIGITAFTOOLS Technical Webinar and Tool Demonstration Series, which is archived and publicly accessible via a dedicated video playlist.** To date, this series has been utilized to disclose the functionalities and operational workflows of tools developed or optimized during the project, ensuring that technical specifications remain transparently available for long-term consultation.

The recordings archived in the repository are generated from a series of thematic webinars conducted between 2025 and 2026, each focusing on specific operational challenges in agroforestry:

- [Carbon Farming \(November 2025\)](#): Focused on digital tools for the planning, measurement, and scaling of carbon sequestration within agroforestry systems, featuring contributions from

EURAF, INRAE, and the Louis Bolk Institute. Training on the Open Farm Carbon Tracker and Farm Carbon Calculator, addressing the technical hurdles of the 90% accuracy requirement in the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF).

- [Financial Management \(January 2026\)](#): Addressed the economic dimension of agroforestry through demonstrations of financial support tools developed by ILVO, Cranfield University, and DeFAF. Demonstration of tools like Farm-SAFE and AgroForstRechner, teaching advisors how to interpret Net Present Value (NPV) and Annuities to secure bank loans for farmers.
- [Biodiversity and Soil Health \(February 2026\)](#): Disclosed tools designed for the assessment and monitoring of ecological indicators, led by researchers from Ghent University and the European Forest Institute (EFI). Hands-on sessions with the Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator (BiodivAF), showing how to use the tool's estimated 16% average biodiversity increase as evidence for certification schemes.
- [Tree Selection and Management \(March 2026\)](#): Provided technical guidance on decision-support systems for species selection, long-term tree management and climate change adaptation, coordinated by INRAE, CIRAD, and ILVO. Coordinated guidance using AgroforesTreeAdvice to help practitioners choose among 160+ tree species based on local pedoclimatic suitability.

To ensure the scalability of these results, DigitAF has established collaborative training actions with related Horizon Europe initiatives, most notably the ReForest project. A key example of this synergy was the [joint webinar "Digital Innovation for Scaling Agroforestry" \(February 2026\)](#), which integrated the ReForest Toolbox with the DigitAF Tool Catalogue. These actions focus on the harmonization of digital monitoring frameworks and ensure that practitioners are presented with a cohesive ecosystem of tools, fostering a shared European knowledge base that supports the long-term professionalization of the sector.

Living Lab Engagement: Engagement is driven by addressing "what keeps farmers awake at night". This includes practical training on machinery—such as offset single-side ditchers for tight spaces and mechanical nut pickers for scaling up production.

7.3. Digital dissemination tools

Dynamic Zenodo–WordPress Integration		https://digitaf.eu/policy-briefings/ https://digitaf.eu/reports-on-deliverables/	
	Type	Open-source dissemination and repository integration tool	
	Objective	Enable a direct, automated connection between the DigitAF (or any other project) website and the Zenodo repository to ensure that project outputs remain accessible, citable, and independent of the project website's long-term availability.	

	Target users	Research projects, website developers, knowledge platforms, and organisations implementing FAIR-aligned dissemination strategies
Current status		DigitAF uses a WordPress shortcode plugin (https://github.com/euraf/wp-shortcode-zenodo) that retrieves records from Zenodo via its API and displays them as web cards. This ensures deliverables and outputs are not stored statically on the website but dynamically pulled from their persistent repository. The system is operational and used for live deliverable and output pages.
Uptake mechanism		Enables reuse by allowing projects to embed Zenodo queries directly into their websites, automatically synchronising new repository entries without manual updates. This reduces duplication and supports FAIR-aligned dissemination workflows.
Long-term sustainability		Decouples website content from storage by relying on Zenodo as the persistent archive, ensuring outputs remain accessible even if the website is discontinued. The open-source plugin can be reused and adapted by other projects.

Agroforestry Permanent Photo Gallery		https://digitaf.eu/agroforestry-gallery/
	Type	Open-access visual dissemination and engagement infrastructure
	Objective	Provide a persistent, web-based visual repository of agroforestry systems, practices, and landscapes across Europe, enabling public access to curated photographic documentation of DigitAF-related activities and case studies.
	Target users	Researchers, practitioners, policymakers, educators, and the wider agroforestry community
Current status		Decentralized, serverless application using the Zenodo EURAF Media community ² as its live database. It retrieves images and metadata via the Zenodo API and displays them in real time using IIIF standards. All assets are stored in a persistent open repository, ensuring long-term availability and synchronization with the DigitAF website. Content moderation is managed at repository level.
Uptake mechanism		Transforms static image collections into an interactive platform supporting dissemination, engagement, and participatory initiatives such as the EURAF photo contest and CAMBIUM project activities. It strengthens stakeholder engagement while introducing FAIR-oriented data practices.
Long-term sustainability		Relies on Zenodo as the persistent storage layer, ensuring durability beyond the project lifetime. The system is fully replicable via open-source code and can be embedded in external websites through simple iframe integration. Photos are

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/euraf-media/>

curated by EURAF assuring legacy quality control and endurance of the gallery.
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8. Monitoring, risks and timeline

8.1. Monitoring framework and key performance indicators

The long-term performance of DigitAF outputs is monitored through a set of practical indicators focused on uptake, visibility, and ecosystem growth. These indicators provide evidence of how digital tools, datasets, and dissemination infrastructures are being accessed, reused, and expanded over time.

Core indicators include:

1. **Number of active users of DigitAF website tools and platforms, including downloads and views of deliverables and policy outputs via persistent repositories (e.g. Zenodo)** (Table 2)

Table 2: Resume of the impact of different components of the Agroforestry Virtual Space and their reach according to reaching factors based on Ingram and Mills (2019).

KPI Indicator	Raw Metric (Direct Access)	Conservative Reach (1:2)	Optimistic Reach (1:5)
Deliverable views	3,046	6,084	15,210
Policy Brief views	23,078	46,156	115,390
YouTube views on tools and their webinars	826	10,200	25,500
Agroforestry photos in gallery	5,870	11,740	29,350
Agroforestry Catalogues	10,444	20,888	52,220

2. **Growth of the catalogues measured through the number of tools and datasets included, and the frequency of new entries and updates over time** (Fig 2)
3. **Evidence of external reuse or integration of DigitAF components in other projects and initiatives**, with evidence provided throughout this report.
4. **Internal uptake of good practices**, with the adoption of FAIR-aligned practices within the consortium, particularly the transition of models towards openly accessible web applications. During DigitAF, these efforts primarily strengthened the Findability and Accessibility of digital resources, as illustrated by the examples presented throughout this report. Future development should place greater emphasis on Interoperability, enabling seamless integration between tools, datasets, and external digital infrastructures through shared standards and APIs.

Figure 2: Temporal evolution of new entries and updates in the DigitAF Tools, Data, and Projects Catalogues since their creation, illustrating the continuous growth and maintenance of the catalogues.

Together, these indicators provide a structured overview of dissemination reach and the continued evolution of the DigitAF ecosystem beyond the project lifetime.

8.2. Key risks affecting long-term sustainability

Data infrastructure dependency - Many DigitAF components rely on external spatial and data infrastructures, including national Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) services and web-based geospatial APIs. While this enables real-time access to authoritative datasets, it also introduces dependency risks related to service unavailability, non-compliance with INSPIRE and High-Value Dataset regulations, and potential discontinuities in national data provision. DigitAF advocates for a

stronger application of the INSPIRE directive, in particular for High Value Datasets such as LPIS data (see Policy Briefing #68, Lawson et al. 2025).

Platform and API stability - Several dissemination components depend on third-party services (e.g. repository APIs, geospatial web services, and IIIF image delivery systems). Changes in external APIs, service downtime, or structural updates may temporarily affect functionality or require technical adaptation.

Fragmented data availability - Despite policy obligations, the availability and completeness of harmonised spatial datasets varies across Member States. Inconsistent implementation of data standards can limit interoperability and reduce the comparability of outputs across regions.

Maintenance capacity and continuity - Although DigitAF promotes open and lightweight infrastructures, the long-term maintenance of tools still depends on institutional commitment, community engagement, and continued technical stewardship. In some cases, continuity relies on key individuals or organisations maintaining active development roles.

Variable community engagement - Engagement from contributors and users tends to fluctuate depending on visibility, events, and project activity cycles. Maintaining consistent participation beyond the project lifetime remains a challenge common to many open research infrastructures.

8.3. Mitigation strategies and resilience design

DigitAF adopts a set of design and governance strategies to reduce these risks and increase system resilience:

- *Decentralised architecture*: tools and outputs are distributed across open infrastructures rather than stored in a single central system.
- *Repository-based persistence*: long-term storage is ensured through open repositories such as Zenodo, decoupling content from website infrastructure.
- *Open-source development model*: codebases hosted on public repositories allow external maintenance, adaptation, and reuse.
- *API-driven interoperability*: systems are designed to consume external data via standardised APIs, enabling substitution or extension where services evolve.
- *Modular ecosystem design*: individual components can be updated or replaced without affecting the entire system.
- *Community-based stewardship*: maintenance responsibilities are shared across research, advisory, and institutional actors, reducing dependency on single project funding cycles.

8.4. Outlook and post-project evolution

Following the end of the project, DigitAF outputs are expected to evolve within a distributed agroforestry digital ecosystem rather than a single controlled platform. Continued development will

depend on a combination of institutional stewardship, community contributions, and integration into future research and innovation initiatives.

The overall trajectory is towards a stable but evolving infrastructure in which tools, datasets, and dissemination systems remain accessible, interoperable, and adaptable, while being progressively improved by the wider agroforestry community.

9. Conclusions

DigitAF establishes a coherent and interconnected digital ecosystem for agroforestry that combines tools, datasets, and dissemination infrastructures within a FAIR-aligned framework, while providing the means to engage. By integrating spatial data, economic models, ecological indicators, and policy-facing outputs, the project provides a functional foundation for evidence-based agroforestry adoption across Europe.

Beyond the project lifetime, its long-term value depends on decentralised stewardship, open-source governance, and persistent repositories such as Zenodo and GitHub. This distributed model ensures that DigitAF outputs remain accessible, reusable, and extensible, supporting continuous innovation and strengthening the role of agroforestry in future European land-use transitions.

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